

PROBLEMS OF ORGANIZING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION**Mamadjonov Ismoiljon Ibragimjonovich**

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the problems of organizing inclusive education in higher education. Inclusive education is important in order to create equal opportunities for all students, and it covers students from different social, economic and cultural backgrounds. The article presents the essence, importance of inclusive education and the main problems that arise in higher education, including the lack of educational resources, teacher training, social stereotypes and infrastructure problems. It also provides suggestions for ways to solve these problems, including increasing resources, training teachers, changing social consciousness and improving infrastructure. The article is considered as an important step towards ensuring stability and social justice in society through the development of inclusive education.*

Keywords: *higher education, inclusive education, upbringing, teacher, student, stereotype, problem, health, economy, global problem.*

The education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is entering a new stage of development in the 11th century, in the context of globalization, technological innovations and socio-economic changes. One of the important issues of the education system is inclusive education, that is, creating equal opportunities for all children, including students with disabilities or experiencing learning difficulties. Inclusive education is important in modern society in order to ensure social justice, implement the socialization of each individual and develop society as a whole.

Inclusive education in Uzbekistan is one of the key topics in the development of the state education system. It is aimed at creating equal opportunities for children with special educational needs to receive education in regular schools. Inclusive education is not only an educational, but also a social project that requires the participation of all segments of society. In Uzbekistan, this area is at the stage of active development, but in order to achieve success, it is necessary to overcome existing obstacles and implement long-term strategic solutions. Inclusive education is an approach to education that provides equal opportunities for all children in obtaining education, regardless of their physical, mental or social characteristics. The topic of inclusion in Uzbekistan is becoming increasingly relevant, especially in terms of fulfilling international obligations, such as the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which was ratified by the country in 2009. However, the process of introducing inclusive education faces a number of problems that require an integrated approach.

The Fund for Support of Social Initiatives in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing the project "Inclusive Education in Uzbekistan" since 2007. The main goal of the project is to create equal opportunities for children and adolescents with disabilities in obtaining education and gradually introduce it into the primary, secondary, secondary specialized and higher education systems, as well as to create conditions for improving the quality of inclusive education. The essence of inclusive education is that its concept has been developed and is being introduced into the preschool and school education system by creating mixed groups and classes on the basis of pilot kindergartens and schools in the cities of Termez, Karshi, Navoi, Samarkand, Jizzakh, Gulistan, Tashkent, Andijan, Fergana, Kokand, Urgench and Nukus.

A distinctive feature of the national model of inclusive education is that it is formed taking into account local and foreign experience. In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 13.10.2020, No. PQ-4860 "On the Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System for 2020-2025", the Concept defines the goals, tasks, main directions, medium- and long-term perspective stages of the development of inclusive education, developed for the purpose of organizing an inclusive education system, guaranteeing and ensuring the right of children with special educational needs to receive education. The Concept defines the goals, tasks, main directions, medium- and long-term perspective stages of the development of inclusive education.

Today, the inclusive education system in Uzbekistan is at the stage of formation. There are specialized educational institutions for children with disabilities in the country, but their number is limited and they do not cover all those in need.

Modern problems of inclusive education in Uzbekistan Today, there are a number of unresolved problems related to the education system, which also includes inclusive education.

Current problems in inclusive education include:

1. Lack of an adequate regulatory and legal framework Despite the existence of laws such as the Law "On Education" and a number of other regulatory documents, many aspects of inclusive education are not spelled out in detail.

2. Lack of qualified personnel Teachers often do not have special training to work with children with special educational needs, which limits the possibilities of effectively implementing an inclusive approach.

3. Material and technical difficulties. Many educational institutions are not equipped for children with physical, sensory or other disabilities.

4. Stereotypes and misconceptions. Society often lacks sufficient information about the importance of inclusion, which leads to discrimination and isolation of such children.

5. Insufficient funding. Inclusive education requires significant investments, from training personnel to creating adapted infrastructure. Successful implementation of inclusion requires coordination of efforts between education, health and social protection systems.

D. B. Zaysev I., I. Loshakova, P. V. Romanov, Ye. R. Yarskaya- Smirnova) analyzed the attitude of ordinary schoolchildren to students with various disabilities. It was found that children were most tolerant of their peers with musculoskeletal diseases. Children with hearing and vision impairments were less tolerant. The lowest level of tolerance was determined in relation to children with intellectual disabilities. From 2006 to 2011, research was conducted in the field of inclusive education abroad.

Thus, A. De Boer, S. J. Peil and A. Minnaert "Attitudes of primary school teachers to inclusion: a literature review." B. Kagran and M. Schmidt Slovenian teachers' attitudes towards inclusion of students with different types of education in school. N. K. French and R. V. Chopra presented an analysis. Teachers who can implement the ideas of inclusion in school. This study is called "The teacher as a manager." The results of this study reflected the complexity of introducing inclusive education into the general school system. It should be noted that some studies have revealed a negative attitude towards inclusive education both from teachers and from parents of children studying in inclusive classes.

Inclusive education is not only an educational, but also a social project that requires the participation of all segments of society. Successful integration of children with special educational needs into the general education system contributes to the development of tolerance,

equality and social justice. In Uzbekistan, this area is at a stage of active development, but in order to achieve success, it is necessary to overcome existing obstacles and introduce long-term strategic solutions, and to achieve these goals, it is necessary to strengthen the legislative framework, develop infrastructure and continue to form an inclusive consciousness in society.

The development of an inclusive education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is of great importance, which will ensure the fair, equal and sustainable development of society. Integrated approaches and cooperation are necessary to solve existing problems. By training teachers, improving school infrastructure, changing social stereotypes and increasing economic resources, Uzbekistan can successfully implement inclusive education and create equal opportunities for all members of society.

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